

Fig S1 Size distribution by intensity results from DLS measurements of mixtures of the formulation in the presence of increasing SLAE concentrations before vs. after freeze-drying and powder reconstitution

Fig S2 Compiled results of size distribution by intensity obtained along the colloidal stability study in SIF (0h to 4h) with the formulation freeze-dried with SLAE